

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A Comparative Investigation of PETG Material Using Experimental and Simulation-Based Methods

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Abstract

Objectives: The primary objective of this research article is to compare the mechanical properties of polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) with other commonly used 3D printing materials. The study focuses on conducting a comparative evaluation of PETG based on its tensile and flexural properties through practical laboratory testing, followed by validation of the experimental results using Finite Element Analysis (FEA). **Method:** The 3D models were first designed using SolidWorks software and then sliced to produce the physical specimens. These specimens were subsequently subjected to tensile and flexural tests in accordance with ASTM standards to evaluate their strength. The process further included conducting experimental tests and comparing the obtained results for performance evaluation. After conducting tensile testing, the ultimate tensile strength of the material, tensile load, and elongation at break were checked. **Findings:** The ultimate tensile strength obtained after conducting tensile test in ANSYS was 56.46 MPa. The average ultimate tensile strength after experimental investigation was found to be 47.58 MPa. Similarly, when exposed to flexural stresses, a flexural test discovers a large number of significant properties of a material. The flexural strength obtained after conducting flexural test in ANSYS was 77.01 MPa and the average flexural strength after experimental investigation was found to be 66.96 MPa. The numerical results showed good correlation with the experimental findings. **Novelty:** The present study aims to establish a comparative experimental-numerical framework for evaluating PETG behaviour under tensile and flexural loading conditions while analysing the influence of printing parameters such as layer thickness on mechanical performance.

Keywords: PETG; FEA; Material Properties; Additive Manufacturing

1 Introduction

FDM is a solid-based extrusion method, which has become the most popular method of operation because it is easy to use, low-cost equipment, and can be used with a large variety of thermoplastic materials⁽¹⁾. As a promising FDM material, Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG) has become a subject of great interest in recent times and is able to fill the performance gap between PLA and ABS. PETG has been used due to its good combination of mechanical strength, flexibility, chemical resistance, low moisture absorption, high layer adhesion, and low warping during printing⁽²⁾. Past studies have established that FDM-printed components have anisotropic mechanical performance, in part because interlayer fusion and directional bonding between the layers cannot be perfect⁽³⁾. Consequently, the optimization of printing parameters and the mechanisms of material behavior under various loading conditions have become key research topics in additive manufacturing. A number of recent investigations have been aimed at assessing the mechanical performance of PETG components produced with the help of FDM. The study investigates the feasibility of employing 3D printing technology to fabricate reference specimens for validating compressive strength measurements in construction laboratories. Polylactic acid (PLA) and polyethylene terephthalate glycol-modified (PETG) were selected as the printing materials owing to their widespread availability and extensive use in fused deposition modeling (FDM)⁽⁴⁾. Other studies aim to examine the influence of infill ratio and infill pattern on the dynamic mechanical properties of polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) printed structures⁽⁵⁾. The effects of key Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) process parameters—namely layer thickness, raster angle, and infill percentage—on part weight (PW), build time (BT), maximum failure load (MFL), and elongation at break (E) of polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) were systematically investigated using a design of experiments (DOE) approach⁽⁶⁾.

In addition to unfilled PETG, efforts have been made in terms of reinforcing PETG with fibers and fillers in order to enhance the mechanical performance of the material even more. The research on glass-fiber and carbon-fiber-reinforced PETG composites has shown significant tensile, flexural, and compressive strength enhancement over neat PETG⁽⁷⁾,⁽⁸⁾. It has been investigated to develop hybrid composite formulations with expanded graphite and other fillers to balance between mechanical strength and thermal stability⁽⁹⁾.

Although several studies have investigated PETG mechanical properties, limited research has systematically combined experimental tensile and flexural characterization with numerical validation using FEA for unreinforced PETG fabricated through FDM. The present study aims to establish a comparative experimental–numerical framework for evaluating PETG behaviour under tensile and flexural loading conditions while analysing the influence of printing parameters such as layer thickness on mechanical performance.

2 Methodology

The Figure 1 represents a workflow in material testing from ‘creating 3D models’ and ‘printing the models’, which will give us physical objects. These objects are then subjected to ‘tensile and flexural testing’ to determine their strength. The subsequent procedures involve ‘finite element analysis and ‘comparing results’ for performance evaluation. Finally, the findings are examined in terms of “analysis and conclusion”.

Fig 1. Methodology adopted

To determine the strength of Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol, samples were tested with varying layer thicknesses. Each sample setup followed the ASTM guidelines. During the testing phase, controlled pressure was applied to each sample until it reached its breaking point. This approach enabled to evaluate the strength of PETG and understand how variations in layer thickness significantly affect its properties. For tensile strength measurement, a specimen is prepared according to guidelines (ASTM D638) to ensure uniform failure during testing. Once the specimen setup is complete, force is applied gradually while continuously measuring both the applied load and the elongation of the specimen. For flexural strength measurement, a test specimen is prepared in accordance with the specified standards (ASTM D790) and subsequently mounted on a flexural testing

machine. A controlled force is then applied at one or more points on the specimen, and the resulting deformation is measured and recorded at the points of load application. In this study, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was employed to analyse stress distribution and deformation patterns under bending loads. Unlike many previous studies that focused solely on experimental testing, this research validated the results through numerical simulation. Parameters such as tensile strength, yield strength, elongation, elastic modulus, and Poisson’s ratio were considered in the numerical evaluation of tensile and flexural behaviour. This idealization arises because the numerical model does not account for manufacturing-induced defects, such as voids and interlayer discontinuities, and assumes ideal material behaviour. Nevertheless, the strong correlation between experimental and numerical results demonstrates the effectiveness of FEA as a reliable tool for design support and validation, thereby fulfilling the objective of this research. The comparative analysis of the tensile and flexural testing was done experimentally and numerically. A mesh convergence study was conducted to ensure numerical stability. Boundary conditions were applied according to ASTM loading configurations. The model assumed isotropic linear elastic material behaviour. The modeling details are as follows –

- Mesh element size – 10 mm
- Number of elements – 66
- Support and loading conditions – Fixed support and centrally applied force

Table 1 shows the printing parameters considered while printing the specimens.

Table 1. Printing Parameters and Fabrication Conditions

Parameter	Specification
Printer Model	AION 500 MK2 printer
Nozzle Diameter	0.4 mm
Nozzle Temperature	240 °C
Bed Temperature	80 °C
Layer Thickness	0.2 mm
Infill Density	100%
Infill Pattern	Rectilinear
Raster Angle	±45°
Print Speed	50 mm/s
Cooling Fan Speed	40%
Build Orientation	Flat

All specimens were fabricated using Ultimaker Cura slicer software and printed under controlled laboratory conditions at $27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ ambient temperature. The details regarding the material used, software used are mentioned below.

- PETG filament diameter - 1.75 mm
- Filament manufacturer - eSUN
- Ambient temperature during printing/testing - $27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$
- Universal Testing Machine (UTM) - INSTRON (Model - BISS) UTM
- ANSYS software version – ANSYS 2024 R1 Student version
- Slicing software - Ultimaker Cura slicer

Although the current study used three specimens per condition according to preliminary validation requirements, future work will involve larger sample populations for enhanced statistical confidence. The novelty of the present study lies in its combined experimental and numerical analysis of PETG under tensile and flexural loading conditions. While previous research has primarily focused on tensile behaviour or reinforced PETG composites, this study establishes a clear mechanical baseline for unreinforced PETG and demonstrates the effectiveness of FEA in predicting its mechanical performance.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 Results for tensile testing

After conducting Tensile Testing, the result obtained for PETG is the ultimate tensile strength of the material, tensile load, and elongation at break. PETG usually has a high tensile strength and high elongation, thereby enabling it to serve as an ideal

material in applications where the strength and elasticity are vital, including automotive materials, medical tools, and other consumer products. PETG’s stress-strain curve graphically explores how the material reacts when exposed to high tension. For the specimen (ASTM-D638), we have taken the dimensions as - Width: 13 mm, Thickness: 4 mm, Cross Section Area: 50 mm².

Figure 2 shows Load vs. Displacement Graph for Tensile Testing and Figure 3 shows specimen after tensile testing. The load applied is 2673N. The result obtained after conducting the Flexural test in ANSYS is 56.46 MPa.

Fig 2. Load v/s Displacement Graph for Tensile Testing

Table 2 shows the results obtained after conducting the Tensile Testing on the specimen ASTM – D638.

Table 2. Experimental Results of Tensile testing

Sr. No	Tensile Load (N)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)
1	2673	52.76	3.16
2	2296	45.29	4.00
3	2232	44.30	6.60
Average	2400	47.45	4.58

The experimental results of the present study revealed the average ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of PETG to be 47.45 MPa and the average elongation at break to be 4.58%. These values are in line with earlier findings of unreinforced PETG printed by FDM. Hsueh et al.⁽¹⁾ noted that optimized printing settings can produce PETG tensile strength similar or a little better than PLA, with a better ductility. The tensile strength obtained in this study is relatively lower compared to carbon-fiber- or glass-fiber-reinforced PETG, which has been reported to be more than 60 MPa under favorable conditions⁽⁸⁾. There is good correlation between experimental tensile data and numerical data obtained using Finite Element Analysis (FEA). The calculated tensile strength of 56.46 MPa had a reasonable error against the experiment mean.

Fig 3. Specimen (ASTM D638) post Tensile Testing

3.2 Results for flexural testing

When exposed to bending or flexural stresses, a flexural test reveals important flexural properties of a material. Since a material is likely to be used in application environments where bending forces are applied, the results are crucial. The specimen used had the dimensions Width: 20 mm, Thickness: 4 mm, Span: 61 mm. Figure 4 shows FEA result for flexural testing. And Figure 5 shows Load v/s Displacement graph for flexural testing. Figure 6 shows the flexural specimen after testing. The result obtained after conducting the flexural test in ANSYS is 77.01 MPa.

Table 3 the results obtained after conducting the Flexural Testing on the specimen ASTM – D790.

Table 3. Experimental Results of Flexural testing

Sr. No	Flexural Load (N)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
1	223	67.89
2	213	65.89
3	215	67.13
Average	217	66.96

The mean experimental flexural strength was 66.96 MPa in this experiment, with the FEA calculated value of 77.01 MPa. Earlier studies have indicated flexural strengths of PETG to be 60-75 MPa, depending on the infill geometry and process parameters⁽⁸⁾. Simulated strengths were slightly higher than measured ones, and the results of the FEA were reasonably consistent with experimental values of both tensile and flexural tests. This idealization is explained by the fact that idealized material assumptions, as well as manufacturing-induced defects, e.g., voids and interlayer discontinuities are not considered in the numerical model. The reduction in tensile strength compared to simulation results can be attributed to weak interlayer diffusion and internal voids generated during the FDM deposition process. Flexural loading subjected outer layers to tensile-

Fig 4. FEA result for ASTM - D790

compressive stress combinations, making interlayer adhesion a dominant factor influencing failure behaviour. Small differences between experimental and numerical results are attributed to manufacturing defects, internal porosity, imperfect interlayer bonding, and anisotropic behaviour not fully captured in the simulation. Layer thickness is a key factor in defining the mechanical performance of PETG. PETG-CF composite exhibited an optimal tensile strength of 29.4 MPa under the printing parameters of 0.20 mm layer thickness, 45% infill density and 70 mm/s printing speed⁽¹⁰⁾. Kumaresan et al.⁽¹¹⁾ and Doshi et al.⁽¹²⁾ found that decreased layer thickness enhances interlayer bonding, and consequently, tensile and flexural strength. Also, the built time decreases when the layer thickness is increased⁽⁶⁾. These findings are supported by the consistent results achieved in the current study and further justify the importance of considering the layer thickness as an important parameter when fabricating PETG parts. Printing parameters strongly affect interlayer diffusion, void formation, and residual stress development, thereby influencing the tensile and flexural strength of PETG components⁽¹³⁾. Microstructural characterization such as SEM-based fracture surface analysis was not included in the present study and will be considered in future investigations to better understand interlayer bonding and failure mechanisms.

4 Conclusion

The present study experimentally and numerically evaluated the tensile and flexural behaviour of FDM-printed PETG specimens. The results demonstrated reasonable agreement between experimental and simulation outcomes, indicating the usefulness of FEA for preliminary prediction of PETG mechanical performance. Following conclusions are made from the research –

1. The tensile strength of PETG was found to be 47.45 MPa with an average elongation at break of 4.58%, indicating good ductility compared to commonly used FDM materials such as PLA and confirming its ability to withstand mechanical stress without brittle failure under ASTM testing condition
2. The flexural strength obtained through ANSYS simulation was 77.01 MPa, while the average flexural strength determined from experimental testing was 66.96 MPa, which demonstrates that PETG is highly resistant to flexural stresses.

Fig 5. Load v/s Displacement Graph for Flexural Testing

Fig 6. Specimen (ASTM D790) post Flexural Testing

3. The study systematically compared experimental testing and numerical simulation to evaluate the mechanical performance of PETG under tensile and flexural loading conditions. The numerical results showed good correlation with the experimental findings.

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